

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

The Post-COVID-19 Transition from Algebra I to II:
A Cohort Study on a Small Public High School in Long Island, New York

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

Abstract

This study aimed to determine if A: the COVID-19 pandemic played any role in the academic self-efficacy (ASE) of students taking Algebra II of the Class of 2025 in New York State (NYS), and B: if the change in ASE correlated with students' work performances, adhering to the Bandura theory of self-efficacy. Prior research indicates that the pandemic has indeed played a role in negatively influencing students' ASE, considering its restriction on learning and the struggle of schools to get back on their feet. Research has yet to be conducted on how the pandemic specifically shaped the ASE of students taking a capstone course, considering that schools shut down when the students took the introductory course. Research has also yet to be conducted on how this change has influenced individual work performance in high school students. Data was collected through the distribution of a survey, including qualitative analysis. Quantitative analysis questions were applied through Likert-scale questions using the ASES and IWPQ scales to determine if the initial hypothesis was true, that the pandemic adversely influenced both scales. A percentage difference test was first used to see if there was any difference between the ASES scores in the survey and another study examining ASES scores before the pandemic. Spearman's rank coefficient of correlation test was used to see if there was any correlation or significance between the ASES and IWPQ scores received from participants in my survey. Multiple conclusions were made from this study, with one being that there was a significant percent difference between the ASES scores of my survey and the ASES scores of studies performed before the pandemic, proving that the pandemic must play some role in the loss of ASE for students. Secondly, there was a moderately positive correlation between ASES and IWPQ scores, proving that the change in ASE affected a student's perception of their work performance. This information further adds to the body of knowledge on the correlation between

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

the pandemic and ASE for students, along with its change in work performance, to a more specific extent. More studies should be conducted replicating this research to focus on how the pandemic shaped ASE for different genders, races, or religions, as well as testing on grades below the Class of 2025 since the sudden change in learning algebra might also impact them. If this research is further studied, the limitations found in this research should be considered, such as the smaller sample size analyzed and the limited time to conduct the study. However, they should still be able to yield similar results to this study.

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

Introduction

The importance of Algebra and its role in society is commonly underestimated. Algebra can even be considered an ultimate “gatekeeper” course for college and workforce preparation (Choike, 2000). However, its practical applications in various fields can only be utilized through congruous education and mentorship. In high schools, a teacher’s role is to help students apply Algebra by developing structured curricula that sadly entail time, resources, and support (Menzel & Clarke, 1996).

The idea of adopting algebra into a school’s curriculum was first raised in the early 1690s when the renowned Sir Isaac Newton suggested that all Royal Navy academies teach “artificial arithmetic,” also known as Algebra. However, Newton’s doctrine was not introduced until the 1800s. Many schools during the 1800s designated specialized Algebra courses to assist students in modeling real-world scenarios and to prepare students for secondary schooling (Ellerton et al., 2017).

Contemporary society continues to place a similar emphasis on learning Algebra worldwide. Every high school state-wide standardized test in the United States includes a math portion heavily composed of Algebra (Miller, 2022).

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

Likewise, New York State (NYS) administers the “Regents” examination every year in January, June, and August. These exams were designed as achievement tests that aligned with NYS learning standards. They are seen by school personnel as a means to identify learning goals, by educators as a guide to understanding essential concepts, and by students to receive college credit (New York State Next Generation Mathematics Learning Standards, 2019). For every public high school in NYS, 22 credits are required for a student to graduate, including three in the mathematics department. The three required mathematics courses to graduate are Algebra I, Geometry, and Algebra II/Trigonometry. For my study, I will solely focus on Algebra I and II.

The Algebra I Regents course is the first mathematics Regents course typically taken in eighth or ninth grade. According to the NYS Regents Examination Standards, by the end of eighth grade, students should be able to precisely explain and analyze the process of solving an equation (New York, 2019). Similarly, the Algebra II Regents course is the capstone of the three mathematics Regents courses. This course builds up to the fundamental concepts taught in Algebra I by introducing new types of functions, such as logarithmic and exponential. Additionally, this course assesses the trigonometric aspects of functions by adding what was taught in the Geometry Regents course. It is essential to understand how much Algebra I is used in Algebra II since the course is practically a continuum of the other. The transition to such a course can be heavy for many students, especially since one must remember what they learned in Algebra I to understand what is being taught in Algebra II.

The COVID-19 pandemic, which originated in 2019 and had its climax from 2020 to 2021, played a significant role in how these courses were taught and assessed. All June and August 2020 Regents exams were canceled due to violations of social distancing while taking the exams. All 2021 Regents exams allowed schools to have students either take the test for

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

educational purposes or be exempt from the exam. Both options guaranteed students college credit for that course (Jorgensen, 2021). Generally, this pandemic changed the course of learning techniques as it required all schools to teach their students virtually or to incorporate a hybrid learning system (Zamchiya, 2020). This would cause future trouble for NYS students since both the learning environment and testing etiquette have drastically altered their perspectives of learning in Regents courses, especially considering environmental factors.

The environmental factors must address these students' academic self-efficacy (ASE). Academic self-efficacy is an individual's conviction that they can achieve academic tasks or attain an educational goal at a designated level (McGrew, 2008). This concept is grounded in the self-efficacy theory (Bandura, 1977) and has been used to determine a loose hierarchical multidimensional structure for self-achievement. Self-efficacy is believed to impact the performance and the rate at which one completes tasks and sufficiently does so. Research has shown that a high ASE creates a feeling of calmness and serenity when approaching difficult questions, while a low self-efficacy proved the opposite (Eccles et al., 2005). This concept manifested in NYS schools as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic.

There is a problem with or with the need for foundational algebra skills, as seen in NYS students after the pandemic. Despite statewide efforts to mediate the situation by integrating sufficient learning techniques into these students, students still need help with confidence and self-efficacy in secondary math courses, such as Algebra II. This problem has negatively impacted students of the Class of 2025 and their teachers because students struggle to motivate themselves to learn in said math courses, and teachers struggle to encourage the students (Firmansyah & Bandonno, 2022). A possible cause of this problem is the sudden and disruptive switch to virtual learning and the conditions of virtual learning, such as being exempt from the

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

Algebra I Regents exam. A study investigating these students' self-efficacy and its relation to academic performance through surveying these concepts could alleviate the issue.

Literature Review

Before the global crisis 2020, Algebra was always assumed to be a distasteful and unamusing subject in most high schools. Moreso, transitioning from Algebra I to any secondary mathematics course has often been a struggle for students. K. Abdul Gafoor and Abidha Kurukkan investigated potential reasons students perceive any mathematics course negatively. Their studies resulted in the idea that self-efficacy plays a significant role in the perceptions of math. The thought process of “I cannot do math” is popular with most students, especially in an Algebra course, where they lose hope simply because they think it is a complex subject.

Additionally, most students gave up learning mathematics because they needed a firm background knowledge of the topic (Gafoor & Kurukkan, 2015). This holds excellent regard to the transition from Algebra I to II or any secondary mathematics course since evidence supports claims that a lack of foundational knowledge in Algebra or any introductory mathematics course impairs a student’s capability to succeed in secondary classes. Existing research about students’ contributions towards learning algebra has shown that there has been a variety of errors made by students in terms of efficacy of learning and intuitive thinking, such as assumptions, a lack of understanding of algebraic syntax, and psychological factors such as anxiety and a lack of motivation (Egodawatte, 2009). Notably, there has always been a stigma against learning Algebra due to its supposed difficulty, preventing students from trying to understand the concepts being taught because of the communal distaste towards Algebra.

Taking the recent COVID-19 pandemic into account, this situation is highly intensified. The pandemic has been proven to affect education in general, as it is especially seen in the

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

mathematics department. When the pandemic first set off in NYS in 2020, it was announced by the NYS Department of Education that all schools would be closed until April 20, in addition to the mandatory installation of virtual learning effective March 23, 2020. This sudden disruption in education led to many hindrances in NYS that made learning hard: parents lacking proper childcare, students lacking digital devices and internet connectivity, and stark internet disparities. The discrepancy between owning a device and being able to attend online courses led to only 85% of students attending these courses, in comparison to 92% of students attending in-person instruction before the pandemic (DiNapoli & Jain, 2021). The spring 2020 semester was challenging for many NYS school districts. A study connecting these disruptions of pandemic learning with middle school-level education showed that the high-achieving middle school who received A or B grades before the pandemic were shown to receive lower grades after the pandemic, typically due to a lack of motivation (Kuhfeld et al., 2022, pp. 245-261). The researcher in this study noted that it was imperative to provide sufficient educational programs to middle school students during the crisis so that students could develop self-determination and self-efficacy skills to maintain their academic stability.

From a student's perspective, one might not realize how much the pandemic has impacted their learning and overall educational stability. Glenn Stone and many others investigated the case study of a 16-year-old student named Aaliyah. Before the pandemic erupted, Aaliyah was involved in several extracurricular activities and was a straight "A" student. The outburst of the pandemic and the sudden closures resulted in Aaliyah barely getting to socialize or engage in extracurricular activities. Her straight "A's" before the pandemic plummeted as she barely tried to pass the sources since it was challenging to keep up in such an environment (Stone et al., 2022). Aaliyah's story can relate to most adolescents during this time of disparity. Given the

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

previously mentioned stigma against learning algebra and conceptually understanding mathematics, this pandemic would significantly harm this issue since many students are not motivated and pay little attention to virtual courses.

A critical discussion that must also be discussed is how the pandemic impacted students' ASE. A general basis of self-efficacy is provided in numerous research papers. One proves that ASE increases positive feelings, task performance, and net academic success (Taufiq-Hail, 2022). Given that the pandemic has resulted in an overall negative impact on the motivation and drive of students, the self-efficacy of students, which lies under these categories, would also be diminished due to the pandemic. The pandemic and its academic restrictions have proven to escalate anxiety levels and mental health disorders (Ma et al., 2021). Additionally, the switch in the learning style made students need more preparation for their college entrance examination (Omotoy, 2023). This is all about self-efficacy as a student's general morale and capability to succeed in a course derive from the human mind.

Algebra is crucial to understanding and comprehending what is taught in secondary mathematics courses. For example, emerging research suggests that students who have taken algebra as early as the eighth grade have shown to have more excellent success rates in secondary mathematics courses (Knuth et al., 2016). Even so, this research has been supported and proven when tested on secondary school students. A study was performed by Ashley L. Suominen, where results have shown that most undergraduate students need help understanding even the most fundamental concepts of an algebra course as they partake in college-level mathematics material (Suominen, 2018).

Many even highlight the importance of taking algebra, specifically in the eighth grade. It has been argued that taking a fundamental and introductory algebra course as early as eighth

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

grade would be beneficial to students since many would find it easier to learn, and it would benefit them greatly when students attend high school and take rigorous mathematics courses that would heavily involve algebra (Usiskin, 1987). Researchers have supported this claim, as Julia B. Smith acknowledges the long-term benefits of learning algebra, specifically in the eighth grade, such as in college courses and even in the workforce (Smith, 1996, pp. 141-153).

Note: The mean scores for the Algebra I Regents Examination for NYS Public School by Year

Above is a figure representing the mean score for the Algebra I regents examination for NYS public schools from 2015-2023. It is noted that the average percentile of scores drastically dropped in 2020-2021, with as low as 18% being the mean score around this period, compared to 60-80% in previous years. Reasons that can account for this disparity would be the option to be exempt from the exam during the 2020-2021 season, a loss of learning, or insufficient education during this season. This is the exact year when the NYS Class of 2025 takes on the course and chooses to opt out of the exam, which leads to the gap in my research.

The Gap

The recurring stigma against learning algebra and the struggle to transition from Algebra I to II, or any secondary mathematics course, has been present for students, especially in NYS. Given that this state-enforced virtual learning during the 2020-2021 season, in addition to the

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

inherent learning loss from students and motivation loss from teachers, students are likely going to struggle to get back on their feet and strive academically as they would have done if the pandemic were not an issue. I am researching how this learning loss in mathematics and drastic change in education affects the self-efficacy of students taking the Algebra II course, a capstone course, since taking Algebra I during the peak of the pandemic since it is a topic that has yet to be discussed and since every public high school in this state has been required to enforce students to take both courses in chronological order. Furthermore, there needs to be more current research on the impact of the pandemic on taking an introductory course and how that has affected the ASE of a capstone course. While studies done by Imaculada Alemany-Arrebola, for example, studied the impact of the pandemic on the self-efficacy of certain classes, they still needed to look into the aspect of the introductory/capstone course relationship. Since NYS students in the Class of 2025 took Algebra I virtually without having the option to take the final exam, there must be some disadvantage for them to swiftly transition and succeed in Algebra II, which could significantly impact their ASE. Therefore, I beg the research question: “How has taking the Algebra I Regents course during COVID-19 impacted the academic self-efficacy (ASE) for taking Algebra II for the NYS Class of 2025?”

Methodology

A quantitative study was conducted to understand how taking the Algebra I Regents course in the 2020-2021 academic school year has impacted the self-efficacy in taking the Algebra II Regents course. I sent my survey to a small suburban high school in Long Island, New York, since this school, in particular, followed NYS guidelines to install virtual and hybrid learning during the 2020-2021 school year, as well as shifting the regular route in math education for each student by requiring every student of the Class of 2025 to take the introductory Algebra

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

I course during their 8th-grade year, regardless of their preexisting standing on math. Because of this school's restrictions, every student in the Class of 2025 should be able to complete my survey, yielding more results than many other schools combined.

I selected an online survey to conduct the study because it was the most feasible way to administer it, considering the constraints of using other strategies. Employing an in-person survey and interviews would not work because of the robust and tight schedules of each student in this grade, leaving little to no time to complete the survey. Instead, administering an online survey allowed students to participate whenever and wherever they pleased. Employing an online survey also allows the ability to reach a wide range of students via the Internet and avoids ethical barriers. In addition, I decided to create my survey through Google Forms, enabling me to develop Likert-scale questions quickly and flexibly. Additionally, Google Forms lets me view the responses anonymously and examine data charts for each question based on the responses, which I transferred into Excel for further data analysis.

The design of my survey is based on the goals of my research. Since self-efficacy is further reflected through behavioral performance, which, in this case, ASE, is reflected in academic performance, I based my survey on that. I wanted to determine if taking such a keystone course, Algebra I, in a global emergency has affected the overall ASE of students taking the further-required Algebra II regents course. I also wanted to see how the supposed change in self-efficacy can be seen in their academic performance and well-being, adhering to the Bandura theory of ASE. My survey questions utilized two separate scales: the Academic Self-Efficacy Scale and the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire.

The description of my survey clearly states that those who have yet to take the Algebra I regents course in their eighth-grade school year must not participate in the study for research

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

purposes. Therefore, each participant was guaranteed to be a member of my research focus group. To ensure that no ethical and moral barriers were broken, the beginning of my survey contained parental and informed consent forms and the agreement that my survey would be entirely anonymous.

The next section of both surveys included the first scale I utilized: The Academic Self-Efficacy Scale (ASES). Based on Albert Bandura's self-efficacy theory (2007), the Academic Self-Efficacy Scale assesses the ASE of secondary school students. The scale is based on the idea that the efficacy of the students in each of the dimensions of academic work would contribute to the overall academic efficacy (Gafoor & Ashraf, 2007). The survey curated by Kunnathodi Abdul Gafoor and Muhammed Ashraf selected dimensions of academic work to be tested on the scale, such as learning process, reading comprehension, memory, etc. There were 40 questions in the questionnaire used by Gafoor and Ashraf. However, I purposefully selected only half of the given questions and even rephrased them to guarantee more student responses and better comprehension and understanding for the students. Although not to the same extent as the original authors, I still wanted to maintain the exact dimensions of academic work in my survey to analyze my data efficiently. Gafoor and Ashraf explored ASE and school image among higher secondary school students in Kerala, India. They concluded that ASE differs among ethnic groups and genders, and academic focus plays a significant role in ASE for a student. Keeping with this feasible and accessible scale, I also changed the points on the Likert scale from “Exactly True-Exactly False” to “Very untrue of me-Very true of me” to make each question more personable and relatable to answer for each participant. To complete my first research goal, I compared the ASES scores of my study to one by Roquia Amor Adormeo performed before the

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

pandemic to see if the pandemic played any part in the change in ASE. Doing so would lead to the reliability and usage of the next portion of my survey.

The next portion of my survey included questions from the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire (IWPQ). I decided to include this scale and the ASES to see the correlation between self-efficacy and academic performance to fully understand the concepts behind the supposed “learning loss” from the pandemic. The IWPQ was recently developed due to the lack of consensus on conceptualizing and measuring Individual Work Performance (IWP). It was created after a systematic review of the various fields of work in which the IWPQ could be tested based on a three-dimensional conceptual framework of IWPQ (Koopmans et al., 2014). Therefore, this questionnaire is suitable for all workers and even students. Sana Rehman used the IWPQ to assess college teachers' motivation and work performance, revealing that emotional distress accurately predicted a lack of motivation and low work performance among college teachers (Rehman et al., 2021). This questionnaire included three portions of IWP: task performance, contextual performance, and counterproductive work performance. I chose which questions to include in my survey to increase the likelihood of participant response by eliminating questions that may not pertain to the participants. Like the ASES, questions were rephrased to make them more understandable and accessible for high school juniors to read.

To accomplish my other research goal of adhering to the Bandura theory of ASE, where ASE can further be replicated in the work performance of a student in a specific field of academic work, I correlated both the ASES and IWPQ scales in my survey. Gurpreet Randhawa, sharing similar research goals to mine regarding this connection, tested the correlation between individual self-efficacy and the work performance of scientists at a national dairy institute. He employed inter-correlation matrices and multiple regression analysis tests to further his argument

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

and concluded that there was a significantly positive correlation between self-efficacy and work performance (Randhawa, 2004). Because I only tested two variables, withholding dimensional analysis of each framework of both scales, I only conducted Spearman’s Rank Correlation test since it tested the correlation between two continuous data sets. Hoping to yield similar results as Randhawa, considering the academic perspective that I am observing, I conducted the same research analysis process as Randhawa to complete my research needs.

Lastly, with the responses collected from each portion of the survey, Google Forms provided data charts containing breakdowns and charts of reactions. I exported these data charts to Excel to create my data charts to visually portray and understand students' academic efficacy and work performance after taking the Algebra I Regents course at the peak of the pandemic. I also used these data charts to conduct further data analysis to achieve the multipurpose of this research.

Findings

My survey yielded 35 responses from students from a small high school in Long Island, New York. Due to the limited number of teachers and administrators willing to distribute the survey, along with the unwillingness of students to complete the study, the sample size was much smaller than intended, but it was still proven sufficient since I could attain appropriate data to analyze. Starting, I compared the ASES scores in my survey to one of a study conducted before the pandemic (Adormeo et al., 2024) to test if COVID-19 caused any changes. I also compared mean values of ASES and IWPQ scores through p-values and Spearman’s rank coefficient of correlation test.

Figure 1

ASES Scores (\bar{x})	
Before COVID-19:	3.24833333

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

After COVID-19:	3.0254
PD (Δ):	7.11%

To test whether or not COVID-19 yielded any change in ASE for the participating students, my study was compared to the study of (Adormeo et al., 2024), who used the same scale (Gafoor & Ashraf, 2007) before COVID-19. Given that this study was conducted in 2023-2024, and COVID-19 peaked three years prior, a pre-post research study was not possible; therefore, the only replicable and reasonable method of analysis was to compare my study to one that has been done by students of similar age ranges before the pandemic. Visual analysis demonstrates that the mean scores for the ASES for students have decreased since the COVID-19 pandemic, with a percentage difference of 7.10688%. Thus, there is a moderately significant difference between the two mean scores, proving my hypothesis that the pandemic has indeed played a part in ASES scores.

Figure 2

Spearman's Rank Correlation Test	
Coefficient(r_s):	0.659764648
N:	35
T statistic:	5.043511758
DF:	33
P-value:	1.62272E-05

To see if there was any correlation between average ASES and IWPQ scores, the Spearman’s Rank Coefficient of Correlation test and the p-value test were applied since they compared the correlation between two continuous data sets. From calculating the mean responses from each participant (n=35), the r_s value between the two scales is 0.65976465. Using the guide

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

for r_s values, if the value is from 0.40-0.69, there is a moderate and positive correlation between the two variables. Therefore, there is a moderate connection between ASES scores and IWPQ, thus supporting my hypothesis that the change in ASE scores due to COVID connects to the academic performance of students taking Algebra II. With a p-value of less than 0.01%, my results are highly statistically significant and favor my hypothesis. Therefore, the data indicates statistical significance and is expected to find a similar statistically significant correlation from data analysis.

Discussion

Figure 1 shows a difference between the average ASES scores from a study done before the pandemic and my study. This demonstrates the trend that the pandemic has indeed played a part in students' ASE, resulting in lower scores than pre-pandemic students. Although one must understand that there are many other potential factors to this decline, and the fact that the survey was completed by a different demographic of participants, the pandemic, in general, must be considered even as a factor to the inherent change in ASES scores. My conclusion, as expected, agrees with previous studies. For example, a study performed by Inmaculada Alemany-Arrebola took a different approach to a similar research goal: whether the stressful situation of the pandemic and confinement increased anxiety levels, thus influencing the perception of ASE. Her results concluded that the pandemic did lead to worsened mental health for students, which led to lower ASE levels for students. Knowing that my research is concordant with previous research, I concluded that the pandemic hurt a student's self-efficacy. Since the participants in my study took an introductory algebra course during the pandemic with confinement, their low ASES is now defensible.

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

Figure 2 shows that Spearman's rank correlation coefficient between ASES and IWPQ scored a value of 0.659765. Using the guide for various values of (r_s), my calculated value is within the high ranges for a moderately positive correlation between two variables. Therefore, I concluded that there is a moderate correlation between average ASE scores and work performance. Regarding my study, the change in ASE from the pandemic yielded poorer work performance in students taking the Algebra II regents course. Similar to the findings of my study, research done by Gurpreet Randhawa yielded a significant positive correlation between job-specific self-efficacy and work performance, which signifies that the higher the job-specific self-efficacy one has, the higher work performance one will have (Randhawa, 2004). It is important to note that Randhawa's study found a strongly positive correlation between the two scales, while my study only showed a moderately positive correlation. However, my research and Randhawa's generally observed that the correlation's magnitude is positive.

My overall conclusion for my study on the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the ASE of Algebra II students of the Class of 2025 generally agrees with the findings of other studies conducted in this body of knowledge. For example, Chelsi Ariati found that students' learning motivation significantly influenced their mathematical achievement. Students learning motivation and self-efficacy simultaneously affect students' mathematical achievement, and the pandemic has negatively impacted these factors for mathematical success (Ariati et al., 2021). My conclusions directly agreed with Ariati's findings. Furthermore, a study that tested students' belief in ASE after the pandemic, conducted by Kate Talsma and others in 2021, found that students believed that COVID-19-related changes would negatively impact their capacity to perform in school (Talsma et al., 2021). Talsma's findings in 2021 predicted my conclusions in 2024, considering that the students in Talsma's study and their guesses on ASE give credence to

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

the students in my survey who say how COVID-19-related changes have impacted their academic efficacy and work performance.

Limitations, Implications, & Future Research

Although several conclusions were made from this research, it is imperative to acknowledge the possible limitations that might have inhibited the results. One limitation was that although there were 185 students in the Class of 2025 at the small high school I gave my survey to, I only received 35 responses. This is due to a lack of students willing to complete my survey, either because of its length or the exclusive requirements for taking the survey. With such a small time frame to conduct the study and ask students to participate in my research, I could not use different ASES and IWPQ scales that many other researchers have used either because they cost money or I would have to contact the creator of the items for the scales, which is not feasible for my research. However, these limitations were bettered by understanding my subsequent research steps as I gained a better knowledge of the analysis tools and methods needed to answer my research goals. I found the research of Gurpreet Randhawa's, for example, that went into explicit detail on how he conducted his research and inspired me to correlate the ASES and IWPQ to answer my research question best and fulfill my research needs. Because my findings only refer to a tiny high school in Long Island, New York, only one school out of the many in the entirety of NYS, my results could vary across schools in the state since one may argue that I automatically assumed that one high school represented the whole of NYS students of the Class of 2025. However, my findings are just a cohort study on this high school. Since the school I surveyed, in particular, had a system of virtual-immersive learning during the pandemic in addition to requiring every student of the Class of 2025 to take Algebra I in 8th grade, I figured it was best to conduct a cohort study. This school alone was able to answer my specific

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

research needs and fulfill my research goals. My study can instead be seen as a basis for surveying other schools within NYS to see if my understanding of the pandemic negatively affecting the ASE for taking Algebra II, in particular, could be seen across the state or nation.

The conclusions reached from my research come with numerous implications. For instance, many teachers and administrators could use the findings in my study to acknowledge that their schools may have a learning deficit in mathematics, and the cause of that could be the pandemic. Knowing this information, schools could develop ways teachers can effectively integrate proper learning techniques for students, such as individualized learning processes, and by reaching out to students personally to ensure they understand the material they are learning. Students could also use my conclusions to put in more effort in mathematics since they now know what is causing their slump in learning mathematics. They can reach out to their teachers after class or be more likely to raise their hands when they do not understand something. Additionally, knowing the underlying cause of lower ASE could negate the tendency of teachers to move on in lessons without offering help and negate the stigma of learning algebra since “they do not know how to do it.” This can lead to effective learning within schools, hopefully leading to tremendous success for students taking secondary mathematics courses and having a high chance of getting into college.

My research paves the way for many other studies to be conducted. It would be best if studies that share similar research goals to mine would see if race or gender had anything to do with ASE and work performance. While I asked for demographics in my survey, I later found it unnecessary to ask for such since it does not provide any substance to my research goals. Additionally, further studies should test if the ASE for Algebra II for students of the Class of 2025 is similar or different to those of grades below, such as the Class of 2026 and 2027. This

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

would be to see if taking Algebra I in years after the 2020-2021 school year also hurt ASES and IWPQ scores for Algebra II. The capability of students to perform in mathematics, or any class for that matter, truly depends on their work ethic and belief that they can succeed, and all factors behind the pandemic and a student's background must be considered in the research process of studies to come.

THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

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THE POST-COVID-19 TRANSITION FROM ALGEBRA I TO II

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